

Tactile based robotic skills for optimal cable grasping and cable contour following

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Abstract—The robotic manipulation of deformable linear objects (DLOs) such as cables is currently a challenge. In this work, we propose a set of skills based on data from tactile sensors mounted on the end effector fingertips to allow the robot to optimally grasp a DLO and follow its contour. These skills are applied to perform a wiring operation.

Index Terms—Deformable linear object, DLO tactile based manipulation, DLO grasping, DLO contour following

I. INTRODUCTION

The manipulation of deformable linear objects (DLOs), as cables, is central in fields like automotive and aerospace; however, it often represents a bottleneck due to the difficulties in automating this task. Considering a situation where both the DLO ends are constrained by fixtures (see Figure 1c), we propose a set of robotic skills to accomplish the optimal grasping of a DLO and its contour following based on data from tactile sensors as the one shown in Figure 1a, mounted on the fingertips of the robot gripper (see Figure 1b). These skills can be exploited to perform operations such as cable wiring and collaborative wiring harness assembly. In the literature, few works deal with cable contour following: in [1], authors use tactile sensors to follow the cable contour. However, the method proposed in [1] is applied to DLOs characterized by a low bending stiffness that do not present changes in their curvature and proposes a setup different from the one considered in this work, without an optimal grasping strategy. [2] deals with the task of closing a ziplock bag using reinforcement learning and exploiting data from tactile sensors. The policy is also tested on wires and ropes, experiencing, however, loss of contact.

II. OPTIMAL DLO GRASPING AND CONTOUR FOLLOWING

Exploiting a gripper having fingertips equipped with tactile sensors, each composed of a 5×4 matrix (Figure 1a) of taxels ([3]), we define some skills to optimally grasp the considered DLO and follow its contour. The only information provided to the robot is the rough pose of the DLO portion exiting from the fixture holding one of its ends. The end effector is hence brought in this pose and, thanks to the axial alignment skill (in green in Figure 3) and the planar alignment skill (in orange in

Fig. 1: (a) Scheme and reference frame of the tactile sensor. (b) UR5 robot equipped with the Camozzi Smart Gripper with the tool reference frame highlighted. (c) Considered setup.

Figure 3), the fingertips are aligned with respect to the cable shape. In particular, these skills allow to grasp the DLO along the x axis of the fingertips (Figure 1a), ensuring, thus, the best starting condition to slide along its profile (in red in Figure 3). Since the sensors are characterized by a non-zero offset, this must be computed before performing any skill. The axial alignment skill requires estimating and compensating the angle β , shown in Figure 2b. The fingers, controlled in position, are closed progressively: to determine β , the two tactile sensors must touch the cable with the two columns of taxels at opposite ends, numbered as 1 and 4 in Figure 2b. In this case, it holds $\beta = \arctan(d/l)$. The mentioned configuration can be obtained only if the DLO lays on the x axis of the tool frame. It could happen that only one finger is in contact with the cable, as shown in green in Figure 2a: in this case, the position of the fingers must be adjusted moving along the x and y axes of the tool frame. Once the axial alignment is completed, the DLO shape could present a mismatch in the $x - z$ plane of the tool frame: approximating its shape with a straight line, the misalignment is represented by the angle α , linked to the inclination angle m , and the intercept q in the z direction (Figure 2c). These parameters are computed exploiting the least square method, taking as data the pressure centre of each column of both sensors. A rotation of $-\alpha$ around the y axis and a translation of q along the z axis of the tool frame are then performed to align the fingertips x axes with the DLO shape. After that, the diameter D of the DLO is estimated. This

Fig. 2: Schematic representations of several configurations of the DLO (in red) and the fingertips equipped with tactile sensors.

Fig. 3: Flowchart for optimal DLO grasping and DLO contour following.

skill (in yellow in Figure 3) consists of gradually closing the fingers until both sensors touch the cable so that the distance D between the two sides could be evaluated. Once the diameter is estimated, the contour following skill (in red in Figure 3) is achieved by keeping the gripper open for a quantity D : thanks to the low friction force generated on the DLO during the motion, it is possible to slide along the cable, allowing the taxels to properly sense the DLO profile. The cable may also exhibit a curvature γ in the $x - y$ plane of the tool reference frame (see Figure 2d). A rotation of γ (tuned as a predefined value) around the z axis of the tool frame is hence performed if, considering the two fingertips (A and B), there is a positive difference of pressure among their first columns and a negative one between their fourth columns. Instead, a rotation of $-\gamma$ is performed in the opposite case. As the part in red of Figure 3 shows, after the estimation of α, q, γ , their absolute value is compared to some user defined thresholds and the robot moves to compensate the DLO misalignment, advancing also along the x axis of the tool frame of a quantity Δx (that can assume as values Δx_{max} or a smaller one based on the weighted magnitude of the estimated parameters) at a velocity set to v_{max} or v_{min} .

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND USE CASE

A series of experimental tests involving two DLOs and several configurations are carried out to validate the method. Table I shows the success rates of the skills used to perform optimal grasping and contour following tasks. Finally, the presented skills are exploited to perform a wiring operation, as shown in Figure 4, starting from the setup depicted in Figure 1c. The poses of the intermediate clips i are known together with the corresponding s_i , distances from the DLO end where the cable must be grasped and inserted in the intermediate clips. As it can be seen in the accompanying video, after having properly grasped the cable, the robot follows the DLO contour, keeping track of the travelled distance along the arc

Fig. 4: (a) DLO contour following. (b) Wiring operation.

TABLE I: Success rates of the skills for optimal grasping (OG) and contour following (CF) tested on tubes of PA12 with diameters D_i of 6 and 8 mm in several configurations.

Task	DLO configuration	D_1	D_2
OG	-	14/15	13/15
Diameter estimation	-	15/15	15/15
CF	Straight	15/15	14/15
CF	Slope	28/30	27/30
CF	Sharp curvature	16/20	15/20
CF	Smooth curvature	18/20	16/20
OG + CF	Complex configuration	13/15	12/15

length of the cable. As soon as a distance s_i is reached, the robot stops, closes the gripper, inserts the grasped portion of the DLO into the corresponding intermediate clip and then continues to follow the DLO contour.

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